

Morphing wingtip structure based on active inflatable honeycomb and shape memory polymer composite skin: a conceptual work

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Morphing wingtip Concept

- Morphing wing technologies for aircraft designs are receiving significant attention due to their potential benefits to extend the flight envelope of classical fixed-wing aircraft. The lift to drag ratio during climb could be improved by the change of the wing span length, and vertex-induced drag during high-speed flight could be reduced by the folding of the wingtip. The maneuverability could also be improved by assisting the control of ailerons, elevators and rudders.
- Shape Memory Polymers (SMP) are considered a variable stiffness material controlled by temperature. The SMP skins alter shape, with their microstructure in rubbery state at low stiffness, and can withstand aerodynamic loads in the glassy state with high stiffness. SMP skins have been already evaluated for morphing chord wings, folding, deployable, and variable camber wings.
- This work presents a morphing winglet concept based on active inflatable honeycombs and Shape Memory Polymer Composite (SMPC) skins:
 - The wingtip rests in a deployed state with a larger physical aspect ratio wing (a) during take-off and climb phases. The lift/drag ratio can be improved for shorter takeoff distances
 - When the configuration of the wingtip needs to be changed (i.e., flap-up to reduce the induced drag or modify the roll rate) the SMPC skin should be heated to decrease its stiffness. No input pressure to the tubes is applied, but the wingtip flaps up under the pressure differential between the upper and lower surface of the wing. After reaching the designed final position, the SMPC skin is cooled down to become stiff to form a stable winglet configuration
 - The wingtip can again deploy based on the operational flight requirements, and in that case the tubes are inflated after the SMPC skin has been heated up. With a subsequent cooling of the skin temperature, the deploy wingtip configuration is fixed

Modelling analysis

- An actuation geometric and mechanical model that represents the morphing wingtip concept is developed and analyzed.
- The geometric parameters can be selected from the shaded area, i.e. $b=16mm$, $a_1=3mm$, $a_2=11mm$, these parameters are used in the following analysis and design.

Allowable design envelopes for a_1 and a_2

Curves of α and β versus θ

$$F_1 = (F_{r1} - F_{r0}) = \frac{EI}{\cos(\frac{\theta}{4})} \left(\frac{1}{(r_1 - \frac{r}{2})^2} - \frac{1}{(R_0 - \frac{r}{2})^2} \right)$$

$$F_2 = \frac{EI}{\cos(\frac{\theta}{4})} \left(\frac{1}{(r_2 - \frac{r}{2})^2} - \frac{1}{(R_0 - \frac{r}{2})^2} \right)$$

Morphing skin stiffening using PMFs

- Pneumatic muscle fibers (PMFs) could improve morphing skin's stiffness.
- Simulations and experiments were taken to predict the enhance effect.
- Results of simulations and experiments fits well.
- The enhance effect was obtained.

Testing apparatus to verify the load bearing capacity of the SMPCs with and without pneumatic muscle fibers

SMPC maximum displacements with and without PMF stringers at different input pressures

Maximum displacement comparison between simulations and experiment for SMP skin with the PMFs

Prototype and conclusion

- A prototype of morphing wingtip was fabricated, which has shown the feasibility of this concept for possible morphing wingtip configurations for further application.

Simulacra of the morphing of the wingtip configuration without shape memory polymer skin and with black inflatable tubes at different input pressures

Deployment of the wingtip demonstrator with the SMPC skin

- The concept described in this paper may be further evaluated for the use of small UAVs (less than 800 kg), or for other adaptive structures designs in which shape memory polymers could find their use.